

analysed for $C_{18}H_{18}O_4$ (M^+ 298). The uv spectrum

1

showed only one maximum at 343 nm. The ir spectrum revealed the presence of a chelated carbonyl function (1615 cm^{-1}), a complex aromatic substitution pattern ($1600, 1550, 1125, 745$ and 790 cm^{-1}) and a monosubstituted benzene ring (700 cm^{-1}). The nmr spectrum (60 MHz) δ 7.7 (2H, s, α - and β -protons), 14.06 (1H, s, disappeared on D_2O exchange, chelated phenolic-OH), 2.06 (3H, s, $ArCH_3$), 3.95 (3H, s, one- OCH_3), 4.0 (3H, s, one- OCH_3), 7.43 (5H, m, $5 \times ArH$), 6.03 (1H, s, ArH) showed resemblance with that of aurentiacin. The mass spectrum of this compound m/z 298 (M^+), 297 (M^+-1), 221 (M^+-77 , loss of phenyl nucleus) and 195 (M^+-103 , loss of styrene fragment), was also in accord with aurentiacin (2'-hydroxy-4',6'-dimethoxy-3'-methyl chalcone). Finally, this compound was identified as aurentiacin by direct comparison with an authentic sample¹ (m.m p., co-tlc and super imposable ir spectrum).

The occurrence of aurentiacin (1) is being reported for first time from *D. podocara*.

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Extraction and AAS Determination of Trace Amount of Cobalt in Medicinal Samples

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IN continuation of our work¹, the present communication reports a rapid method of determination of cobalt by AAS after its extraction with a β -diketo liquid chelating exchanger (LCE, $RCOCH_2COCF_3$, with $R=C_9H_{19}$) in chloroform as diluent. The method has been applied in the determination of cobalt in medicinal samples.

Experimental

LCE was prepared in two steps¹ starting from the parent compound, a C_{10} -isomeric monocarboxylic acid, Versatic-10 (Shell Chemical Co, London); a 0.1 M solution in chloroform was used in the present work. A solution of Co^{II} was prepared by dissolving $CoSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ (Sarabhai Chemicals) in double-distilled water and was standardised complexometrically². All other reagents used were of analytical grade or comparable purity.

Absorbance measurements were made with a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer with the following conditions: cobalt hollow cathode lamp current, 9 mA; burner height, 6 mm; wavelength, 240.7 nm; slit width, 1.9 Å; air flow rate, 10 $dm^3\text{ min}^{-1}$; acetylene flow rate, 2.5 $dm^3\text{ min}^{-1}$; working concentration range, 2.5–10.0 ppm cobalt. The pH values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH meter.

General procedure: To a solution containing 70 μg cobalt in a 50 ml separatory funnel, were added dilute ammonia to adjust the pH to ~ 8.9 and tris-buffer solution (2 ml; pH=8.9) and total volume made up to 10 ml. 0.1 M LCE (1 ml) was then added to it and shaken for 1 min and then chloroform (10 ml) was added, shaken and allowed to settle for 5 min. The organic phase was transferred to another separatory funnel and the aqueous phase washed with chloroform (2×5 ml). The resulting solution was stripped back into 0.1 N HCl. The aqueous phase was taken and the volume was made up to 10 ml. The absorbance value of the resulting solution was measured on the AAS using the conditions given earlier. The amount of cobalt was found out from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation: The effect of pH on the extraction with LCE shows that in the pH range 8.7–9.6 cobalt is extracted efficiently. Quantitative extraction (97.22%) of cobalt occurs with chloroform and carbon tetrachloride; the results with other solvents

were 1,2-dichloroethane (88.89%), benzene (80.56%), xylene (75.0%) and methyl isobutyl ketone (25.0%). Chloroform was used in the present work. Cobalt has been completely stripped back from chloroform layer to aqueous layer containing 0.1–3.0 N HCl; 1 min shaking time for extraction or back-extraction was enough. On the other hand, 5 min time was allowed for settling the equilibrium in case of extraction or back-extraction. The amount of extraction of cobalt was measured by varying the concentration of LCE and it was found that extraction increased with the exchanger concentration and completed at 0.20 M concentration.

Separation of cobalt : The separation in presence of various ions were studied under experimental condition within an error of $\pm 2\%$; the results for the separation of 7 μg cobalt are as follows : Na^I , K^I , Li^I (2000 μg each); Ba^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} (1000 μg each); Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Mg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Sn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Ga^{III} , In^{III} (200 μg each); Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} (180 μg each in presence of CN^-); Fe^{III} (250 μg in presence of 1,10-phenanthroline). A 1000-fold excess of chloride, 600-fold excess of nitrate, chlorate and sulphate, and 300-fold excess of cyanide do not interfere in the determination of cobalt in binary mixture. Separation was also possible in presence of more than one ion. Thus the method was tested for separation of 7 μg cobalt in (i) the ternary mixtures : Ba^{II} , Zn^{II} (200 μg each); Cd^{II} , Mg^{II} (200 μg each) and Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} (200 μg each); (ii) the quaternary mixtures : Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} , Pt^{II} (100 μg each in presence of CN^-); Sr^{II} , Sn^{II} , Ga^{III} (200 μg each) and Ca^{II} , Cu^{II} , Pb^{II} (200 μg each in presence of CN^-).

Nature of extracted species : The complex may be considered to be bis-chelated as the plot of $\log D$ against the concentration of LCE gives a straight line with a slope of 2.0. Thus the extraction mechanism of cobalt may be represented as

where subscripts o and a are organic and aqueous phase, respectively.

Application : Various medicinal samples were treated* with nitric acid on a hot-plate at low temperature. The residue was cooled, again nitric acid added and gradually heated to about 400°. The mass was then dissolved in 1 : 1 nitric acid and evaporated to dryness for 2 h on a steam-bath. Finally, the residue was dissolved in water and the volume made upto 50 ml. An aliquot was taken and cobalt was separated by the general procedure mentioned earlier after adding a known quantity to each solution, and then the cobalt content determined. The results for the determination of cobalt in various medicinal samples were found satisfactory. When the sample solution was directly aspirated to the AAS, low absorbance value was obtained due to the effect of various ions present in the medicinal samples. The reliability of the present method has been tested from the recoveries of cobalt after adding various known amounts to a medicinal sample solution. The results of the percentage recovery indicates a good reproducibility of the method.

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